

RAJASTHANI VIRAAH GEET: AN ECOCRITICAL READING OF SEPARATION SONGS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an ecocritical reading of *Viraah Geet*, traditional Rajasthani songs of separation sung by women awaiting their loved ones. It focuses on how nature becomes a powerful mirror reflecting the woman's longing, emotional turmoil, and deep personal desires. Through analysis of four selected songs, the study closely examines the lyrics where natural elements like migratory birds, trees, and changing seasons become powerful metaphorical devices that express the indescribable feeling of separation and longing. This study challenges the conventional interpretation of nature imagery as just a backdrop, instead, nature becomes an active participant in the emotional narrative of the singer. These interactions with nature reveal a deep ecocritical resonance, where the external landscape mirrors the internal emotional landscape of the heart. This paper studies how these songs are rich in emotional expression and rooted in cultural ecocritical consciousness, portraying nature as both witness and companion in the journey of longing, hope, and love. Through this ecocritical reading, the study contributes to understanding how traditional folk music integrates human emotional expression with ecocritical themes, offering insights into cultural-ecocritical relationships in Rajasthani folklore traditions.

KEYWORDS: *Viraah Geet*, Ecocriticism, Nature Symbolism, Rajasthani Folk Songs

INTRODUCTION

Every region in India has its own distinctive form of folk art, reflecting local identity and tradition, and Rajasthan is no exception. Rajasthani folk music is rooted in everyday experiences, making the songs a living archive of the region's history and its emotional landscape. Lok Geet (folk music) of the region encompasses folk songs, ballads, tales, plays, sayings, and proverbs. Folk songs are spontaneous expressions of the people of any region and hence reflect various aspects of life more than any other genre (Shekhawat). Similarly, the people of Rajasthan have found unique ways to reflect their emotions, relationships, and philosophies through their folk music. Rajasthani folk music falls into three categories: Religious or Puranic songs, songs about gods and local deities, historical songs about heroic

adventures, and domestic songs about everyday life for the common people (Sharma). One such powerful and emotional evocative folk music genre is *Viraah Geet*- separation songs, sung by women awaiting the return of their loved ones.

Viraah Geet is rooted deeply in the lives of Rajasthani women. Due to the absence of natural resources in the desert area, Marwari people became traders and entrepreneurs in their pursuit of prosperity. They relocated over the world to capitalize on commercial opportunities (Patankar, Mehta). For more than three centuries, migrant merchant traders from various villages and trading lines in eastern Rajasthan travelled to places in northern and eastern India, Russia, and Central Asia. By the late nineteenth century, they were widely known as "Marwari" (Rathi). These songs emerged when Marwari merchants from Rajasthan migrated to distant cities and trade centres across India for business opportunities and jobs. This widespread male migration became a defining feature of Rajasthan's socio-economic history. Women were left behind with their husbands' families, leading to separation and emotional voids that became the major theme of these songs. The separation and longing experienced by the women gave rise to songs that expressed their yearnings for their loved ones, particularly their husbands. These songs have now become an inseparable part of Rajasthan's folk music history, offering not only a lyrical expression of love and longing but also reflecting cultural memory, historical shifts, gendered emotions, and vivid imagery of the natural world.

This paper explores *Viraah Geet* through the lens of ecocriticism, examining how these traditional songs express emotional longing through nature imagery. Ecocriticism explores the relationship between humans and the natural world, highlighting how they coexist, especially as environmental concerns have become inseparable from contemporary human life (Oppermann). Rueckert says that ecocriticism is the study of literature that uses ecology or ecological principles. And Lawrence Buell defines ecocriticism "as a study of the relationship between literature and the environment conducted in a spirit of commitment to environmentalists' praxis" (Buell). The ecocritical approach aims to move beyond the divide between art and life, and between humans and nature, focusing instead on the deep connections that link them (Oppermann). In short, it is a way of studying literature that centres the Earth, helping people understand their place in the world and how they should treat nature (Paswan). Understanding *Viraah Geet* in this context reveals how these oral traditions are not only emotional artifacts but also ecological texts, encoding environmental memory, seasonal rhythms, and cultural connection to the regional landscape within their verses.

This eco-critical study of *Viraah Geet* aims to highlight the intricate relationship between human emotion and the natural world as expressed in these traditional songs. Through symbolic and poetic use of environmental imagery in these songs, the singers create a shared emotional ecology between themselves and the natural world. These songs serve as valuable cultural artifacts that offer insight into the environmental consciousness of rural Rajasthan. At a time when oral traditions are fading, revisiting *Viraah Geet* helps preserve women's voices, regional history, and a deep-rooted connection with nature.

ECOCRITICAL ELEMENTS IN SELECTED VIRAAH GEET

1. Kurjaan (Demoiselle Crane)

The demoiselle crane is a migratory bird that journeys from Central Asia to Rajasthan and other parts of India to escape the harsh northern winters. The graceful Kurjan's arrival and departure have become a powerful metaphor in folk music and poetry of Rajasthan.

Supno jagai aadhi raat main,

Tane main bataoon man ki baat,

Kurjan ye mharo bhanwar milya dyo ye,

Sandeso mhare piya ne puga dyo ye.

The song uses the ecological imagery of Kurjan as a symbol of longing and separation. The singer is a woman yearning for her beloved, describes being woken by dreams in the middle of the night. She addresses the Kurjan, asking her to deliver a message to her husband. The woman's plea to a bird connects human emotions to the natural world, turning the bird into both a symbol and participant in the woman's journey. This use of a specific migratory bird and its seasonal journey ties the theme of separation to nature, making the bird a powerful ecological symbol of love, longing and hope.

2. Peepli (Sacred Fig)

The peepal tree is known for its sacredness and timeless presence; it holds a very special place in both the ecological and cultural landscape of India. Its ever-growing presence and protective shade through changing seasons make it a metaphor for love, separation, and silent witness of human joy and sorrow.

Baai chaalya chha bhanwar ji peepli ji,

Haanji dhola hogyi gher ghumer,

Baithan ki rut chaalya chaakri ji,

Oji mhari saas saputi ra poot,

Mat na sidharo purab ki chakri ji.

The ecological theme in the song comes from the central image of the peepal tree, a living element of nature and memory. The women recall how her husband planted the tree, and it has grown lush and green. Just when the time came to enjoy its shade together, the husband was leaving for a job in the east. The woman doesn't want her husband to leave, but rather than saying it directly, she uses the tree as an emotional excuse to stop her husband. The peepal tree connects her feelings to the natural world, becoming a silent witness to her love and longing. The imagery reflects ecological themes like growth, seasonal change, and the bond between people and their environment.

3. Purab ki naukri

The song captures the pain of separation experienced by women when her husband leaves home for work in distant lands. The title “Purab ki naukri” refers to a time, during the 18th and 19th centuries, when Rajasthani merchants (particularly the Marwaris) began migrating to eastern parts of India for business.

*Chaandya tere chaanne ji,
Sahiba, Chhaat par ghaali khaat,
Gayo naa raajin baawadyo ji,
Koi raatyun joi baat.*

In this song, the woman expresses her longing and loneliness through simple, vivid imagery. She is lying on a cot, under the moonlight. Her beloved, who left for a job in the east, hasn't returned, and she spends sleepless nights waiting for him. The moonlight is the key element of the ecological imagery, representing silence, solitude, and emotional exposure. Nature reflects her emotional state, calm on the outside, but full of longing within. During her sleepless nights, the moon becomes her silent companion in her loneliness. In this song, the natural world becomes both a mirror and witness to the woman's emotional turmoil.

4. Aajya re batau

Aajya re batau is a deeply emotional song that portrays a woman's emotional vulnerability as she waits alone for her husband. The song captures moments of fear, loneliness, and separation.

Teejan ko tyohar dhola, saawan ki barsaat mein,
Ekli ne dar laage kaali peeli raat mein,
Kadke hai bijli yo jeevdo dare,
Aajya batau khadi neem ke tale.

The songs begin with the women singing that it's the festival of *Teej* and the rains of the monsoon (*saawan*) season. Instead of feeling joy, she is afraid of the night, and her heart trembles in fear when lightning flashes. She says I am standing beneath a neem tree and asks the husband to come home. Monsoon is often tied to reunion in Rajasthani folk songs, here becomes a symbol of emotional intensity and vulnerability. The storm reflects here fear, the night mirrors her loneliness, and the neem tree acts as a silent companion. This strong connection between the woman's emotions and her natural surroundings shows how folk songs intertwine human feeling with the rhythms of nature.

CONCLUSION

This exploration of *Viraah Geet* through an ecocritical lens reveals the profound relationship between nature imagery and emotional expression in these songs. This analysis of the selected songs showcases how traditional musical art forms communicate environmental values. The migration of Marwari merchants that gave rise to these songs created a unique cultural convergence where nature imagery becomes decorative as well as deeply symbolic.

The examined song excerpts show the portrayal of nature in *Viraah Geet*, featuring imagery that connects communities to their natural surroundings while highlighting ecological themes. The ecological motifs in the songs, from vivid natural imagery to metaphorical representation of environmental harmony, demonstrate how these songs go beyond personal grief to engage with the environment in a meaningful way. These songs reveal how *Viraah Geet* artists skilfully use elements from the natural world to articulate innermost feelings and desires that might otherwise remain ineffable. The metaphorical utilization of nature highlights an intimate connection between the human emotional landscape and the natural environment.

Ecocritical theory, in this context, helps understand the deep-seated psychological and cultural bonds between humanity and nature. The songs demonstrate that nature exists in both the external reality of the singers as well as an internal framework through which their experiences can be understood and communicated.

Viraah Geet offers a valuable insight into a cultural tradition that understands and expresses the interconnectedness between human emotional reality and the natural world. These songs are deeply rooted in nature, revealing the close relationship that rural Rajasthani communities shared with their environment. The selected song excerpts show how these folk expressions represent a worldview where ecology and emotion are inseparably intertwined. Thus, *Viraah Geet* emerges as both a cultural document and ecological voice, preserving memory, identity, and the timeless bond between people and the natural world.

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